

**DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES IN GRADES 5–6
THROUGH SCAFFOLDING**

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Annotation: This article highlights the concepts of competence and communicative competence. It also defines methods and approaches of developing communicative competences of 5-6th graders and its features, and how scaffolding method helps to improve one of the subcomponents of communicative competencies with activities.

Keywords: methods and approaches of the communicative competences, scaffolding, activities

Communicative competence is the ability to use language effectively in a variety of social and academic contexts. It is a complex skill that involves a number of different components, including linguistic knowledge, sociolinguistic awareness, discourse competence, and strategic competence (Canale & Swain, 1980).

5th–6th graders are at a critical stage in their development of communicative competence. They are expanding their vocabulary rapidly and learning to use it in more complex ways. They are also developing their ability to communicate in different contexts, such as the classroom, the playground, and at home.

There are a number of methods and approaches that teachers can use to develop the communicative competences of 5th–6th graders. Here are a few examples:

- **Task-based learning (TBL):** TBL is a teaching approach that focuses on providing students with opportunities to complete meaningful tasks using language. This approach can be used to develop communicative competence in all four areas of language skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

For example, a teacher could have students work in pairs or small groups to read a text and then create a presentation to summarize the main points. This task would require students to use their listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills in order to complete it.

- **Project-based learning (PBL):** PBL is another teaching approach that focuses on providing students with opportunities to complete complex tasks over a period of time. This approach can also be used to develop communicative competence in all four areas of language skills.

For example, a teacher could have students work together to create a public service announcement about a social issue of their choice. This task would require students to use their research, communication, and problem-solving skills in order to complete it.

- **Cooperative learning (CL):** CL is a teaching approach that groups students together to work on tasks collaboratively. This approach can help students develop their communicative skills by providing them with opportunities to interact with each other in a meaningful way.

For example, a teacher could have students work in pairs or small groups to complete a comprehension quiz on a text. This task would require students to work together to answer the questions and share their ideas and strategies.

- **Explicit instruction (EI):** EI is a teaching approach that involves directly teaching students about language and communication skills. This approach can be used to teach students about grammar, vocabulary, and other aspects of language, as well as about communication strategies such as turn-taking and active listening.

For example, a teacher could teach students about the different types of conjunctions and then have them identify the conjunctions in a text and explain how they are used.

- **Scaffolding:** Scaffolding is a teaching approach that provides students with the support they need to complete tasks that are beyond their current level of ability. This

approach can be used to help students develop their communicative skills by providing them with the necessary support and guidance.

For example, a teacher could provide students with a graphic organizer to help them plan their writing before they begin. This would help students organize their thoughts and ideas before they start writing.

In addition to the methods and approaches listed above, teachers can also develop the communicative competences of 5–6th graders by:

- Creating a positive classroom environment where students feel comfortable communicating with each other and with the teacher
- Providing students with opportunities to practice their communicative skills in a variety of contexts, such as class discussions, group work, and presentations,
- Giving students feedback on their communicative skills and helping them identify areas where they can improve.

By using a variety of methods and approaches, teachers can help 5th–6th graders develop the communicative competences they need to be successful in school and beyond.

Scaffolding can help 5–6 graders develop communicative competences in a number of ways. For example, teachers can:

- **Provide students with graphic organizers to help them plan and organize their writing.** For example, a graphic organizer could help students identify the main points they want to make in their writing and collect and organize their evidence.

- **Use visuals such as pictures, charts, and diagrams to help students understand and remember complex concepts.** For example, a teacher could use a diagram to show the different components of communicative competence or a chart to compare and contrast different citation styles.

- **Break down writing tasks into smaller steps.** For example, a teacher could start by helping students identify the sources they need to use for their writing. Then, the teacher could help them paraphrase and summarize the information from their sources. Finally, the teacher could help them cite their sources correctly in their writing.

- **Provide students with opportunities to practice using in-text citations in their own writing.** For example, a teacher could have students write an essay on a topic of their choice and require them to use in-text citations to support their claims.

Here are some additional tips for using scaffolding to develop communicative competences in 5–6 graders through in-text citation:

- **Make sure the scaffolding is appropriate for the students' needs.** Some students may need more support than others.

- **Gradually remove the scaffolding as students become more proficient.**

- **Make learning about in-text citation fun and engaging.** Use games, activities, and other creative methods to help students learn about in-text citation.

By using scaffolding, teachers can help 5–6 graders develop the communicative competences they need to be successful in school and beyond.

Examples of scaffolding activities for developing communicative competencies

Here are some examples of scaffolding activities that teachers can use to help 5–6 graders develop communicative competences through in-text citation:

- **Activity 1:** Provide students with a graphic organizer to help them plan and organize a persuasive essay on the importance of recycling. The graphic organizer could include sections for identifying the main points of the essay, collecting and organizing evidence, and drafting the essay.

- **Activity 2:** Show students how to use a variety of sources, such as books, websites, and articles, to find information on the importance of recycling. Help students paraphrase and summarize the information they find in their sources.

- **Activity 3:** Model the use of in-text citation by writing a short persuasive essay on the importance of recycling. Be sure to cite your sources correctly.

- **Activity 4:** Have students written a persuasive essay on the importance of recycling, requiring them to support their claims. Provide students with feedback on their essays.

By using these scaffolding activities, teachers can help 5–6 graders develop the communicative competences they need to be successful in school and beyond.

Scaffolding is a teaching approach that provides learners with the support they need to complete tasks that are beyond their current level of ability. As learners become more proficient, the scaffolding can be gradually removed (Wood, Bruner, & Ross, 1976).

Scaffolding can help 5–6 graders develop communicative competences through in-text citation in a number of ways. For example, teachers can:

- **Provide students with graphic organizers to help them plan and organize their writing.** For example, a graphic organizer could help students identify the main points they want to make in their writing and collect and organize their evidence.

- **Use visuals such as pictures, charts, and diagrams to help students understand and remember complex concepts.** For example, a teacher could use a diagram to show the different components of communicative competence or a chart to compare and contrast different citation styles.

- **Break down writing tasks into smaller steps.** For example, a teacher could start by helping students identify the sources they need to use for their writing. Then, the teacher could help them paraphrase and summarize the information from their sources. Finally, the teacher could help them cite their sources correctly in their writing.

- **Provide students with opportunities to practice using in-text citations in their own writing.** For example, a teacher could have students write an essay on a topic of their choice and require them to use in-text citations to support their claims.

Here are some additional tips for using scaffolding to develop communicative competences in 5–6 graders through in-text citation:

- **Make sure the scaffolding is appropriate for the students' needs.** Some students may need more support than others.

- **Gradually remove the scaffolding as students become more proficient.**

- **Make learning about in-text citation fun and engaging.** Use games, activities, and other creative methods to help students learn .

- By using scaffolding, teachers can help 5–6 graders develop the communicative competences they need to be successful in school and beyond.

Scaffolding is valuable teaching approaches that can help 5–6 graders develop communicative competences through in-text citation. By providing students with the support they need to complete tasks that are beyond their current level of ability, teachers can help students become more proficient communicators.

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